

**LEGAL AND REGULATORY FUNDAMENTALS OF
INTERACTION OF CIVIL SOCIETY AND
GOVERNMENT AUTHORITIES IN THE SYSTEM OF
PUBLIC ADMINISTRATION**

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ABSTRACT

The scientific work analyzes regulatory and legal fundamentals of interaction of CS and the government authorities in the system of public administration in Ukraine for the period 2000-2022. Data from the Government Portal (2023) on the regulatory and legal framework for the development of CS in Ukraine were used for the analysis. The results indicate legislative support for developing CSIs in Ukraine at the strategic level. Compared to the CEE countries, Ukraine has a significantly higher Civil Society Participation Index. The regulatory and

Vol. (37), issue 2- 2023 P. ISSN 2222-7288 E. ISSN 2518-5551

legal fundamentals of interaction of CS and the government authorities in Ukraine began to develop in the early 2000s. The analysis of the changes made to the legislation regulating CSIs' activities made it possible to distinguish the stages of developing regulatory and legal frameworks: 1) the stage of establishing the CS's legal framework in 2000-2013 or the stage before the start of Ukraine's European integration; 2) the stage of integration of the legal framework into EU standards from the beginning of 2014 to 2022 inclusive.

Keywords: civil society (CS), CS's legal fundamentals, civil society institutions, public administration, participation of citizens in CS

6. I. INTRODUCTION

In Ukraine, the regulatory and legal fundamentals of interaction of civil society (CS) and the government authorities are changing along with European integration processes. The development of democratic values requires the active involvement and participation of CS. In the conditions of the Russian-Ukrainian war, the activities of the civil society institutions (CSIs) become even more relevant. During the period of 2021-2022, the number of CSIs and the level of trust in their activities are increasing in Ukraine. At the same time, the legal framework lags significantly behind EU norms and standards. Ukraine is included in the category of hybrid democracy according to the Democracy Index. It classifies states according to the state of elections and pluralism, civil liberties, activities of public authorities, political engagement and political culture of the population, into states of full democracy, incomplete democracy, transition type and authoritarian. In other words, it is a state of transition type. The rating of Ukraine according to the Democracy Index in 2022 was 3,36. Several laws and a strategy for developing civil society were adopted in Ukraine (Freedom House, 2022). However, in general, the state of CSIs is assessed as weak, especially in terms of effective interaction with public authorities at both the state and municipal (local) levels. The issue of interaction of civil society and public authorities is one of the most significant, which depends on the political and legal stability of the democratic regime in the country. One of the conditions for the

JOURNAL OF LAW AND POLITICAL SCIENCES (JLPS)

effectiveness of such a regime in Ukraine is to ensure the transparency of the government authorities' activities, as well as involving civil society in public administration processes.

The changes in the fundamentals of Ukraine's political and economic life after the Revolution of Dignity in 2013-2014, integration into the European and Euro-Atlantic civilizational space, the defense of state independence in the conditions of the annexation of Crimea and the war in the east of Ukraine, democratic reforms of the state apparatus made it necessary to carry out a scientific review of the legal fundamentals of interaction of CS and the government authorities in the conditions of the establishing a democratic legal state in Ukraine.

The purpose of the academic paper is to analyze the state of regulatory and legal fundamentals of interaction of civil society and the government authorities in the system of public administration.

7. II. LITERATURE REVIEW

The legal principles of interaction of civil society and the government authorities in a broad sense are the principles of such interaction and the normative expression of the content and essence of these principles in specific normative legal acts at both the national and local levels.

In the scientific literature, studies of CSIs' activities are mainly focused on their role and importance in solving political, and social-economic problems in the EU, organization, state of financing and implementing CS's development projects (Delvino & Spencer, 2019; Pries, 2019; Sellers, Lidström & Bae, 2020; Arato, 2020; Pierobon, 2022; Králiková, 2022). Anheier, Lang & Toepler (2019) note the complexity, tension and interaction between many governments of G20 and organized civil society. In some cases, relations between the state and civil society have deteriorated. This led to the discussion of the issue of "reduction of space" in expert circles for the functioning of civil society. In the conditions of the pandemic and the transition to more centralized management, the problem of

Vol. (37), issue 2- 2023 P. ISSN 2222-7288 E. ISSN 2518-5551

interaction and the rule of law has intensified. Brechenmacher, Carothers & Youngs (2020) explore the specifics of CSIs' activities during a pandemic: cooperation with businesses and government authorities to support local communities in need of economic assistance. Anheier, Lang & Toepler (2019), Brechenmacher, Carothers & Youngs (2020) note that the complexity of interaction is caused by an outdated regulatory framework that does not take into account the diversity of civil society organizations (CSOs). In response, developing a diversified regulatory framework based on functional functions is suggested. The scientific work of Greskovits (2020) demonstrates the influence of the civic circles movement on Hungarian politics, in particular, establishing the fundamentals of civil society thanks to the movement, consolidation of the main electorate, reform of organizations, public administration apparatus. Anders & Lorenz (2021) examine the illiberal tendencies of some former leaders of democratization and Europeanization in Eastern and Central Europe (CEE), which are seen as prime examples of retreat from democracy. Illiberal tendencies are particularly visible in Hungary and Poland and, to a lesser extent, also in the Czech Republic and Slovakia. As a result, the judicial system has been weakened, the rights of minorities have been limited, and the activities of independent media and several NGOs have been suspended. Borzaga et al. (2020) explore social entrepreneurship in Italy and changing legislation to develop and stimulate it. Hollifield (2020) examines the challenges faced by CSIs in France due to the need to control immigrants.

There are no comprehensive studies of the regulatory and legal fundamentals of interaction of CS and the government authorities in the scientific literature, in particular, the effectiveness of the legal framework as a basis for CSIs' activities.

8. III. METHODS AND MATERIALS

Data available from the international social scientific project Varieties of Democracy (V-Dem) were used to assess the state of civil society in Ukraine,

JOURNAL OF LAW AND POLITICAL SCIENCES (JLPS)

Eastern and Central Europe and to study the effectiveness of regulatory frameworks for interaction of civil society and the government authorities. The research uses the dynamics of the CCSI Civil Society Index to measure the state of civil society in Ukraine and its comparison with the countries of Eastern and Central Europe. The index makes it possible to assess the extent to which society enjoys autonomy from the state, the freedom and activity of citizens in the pursuit of political and civil interests. In particular, the following components of the Index were used, namely:

1. The degree of participation of civil society organizations in the consultations (CSO consultation):

Answer options: 0: No. There is a high degree of isolation of the government from the participation of CSOs. The government may sometimes involve or mobilize CSOs after passing laws, but the government rarely consults with CSOs. 1: To some extent. CSOs are just one set of voices that politicians sometimes take into account. 2: Yes. Significant CSOs are recognized as stakeholders in important policy areas and are given the right to vote on such matters. This can be achieved through formal corporate arrangements or less formal arrangements.

2. The degree of self-organization and participation, which measures the diversity and voluntary participation of CSOs (CSO participatory environment).

Answer options: 0: Most associations are funded by the state, in which a large number of active people may be involved, but their participation is not purely voluntary. 1: Voluntary public organizations exist, but few people participate there. 2: There are many different CSOs, but the population's participation is minimal. 3: There are many different CSOs. In society, it is considered normal for a citizen to participate in at least one CSO.

3. Assessment of women's access to participation in civil society organizations (CSOs) (CSO women's participation).

Vol. (37), issue 2- 2023 P. ISSN 2222-7288 E. ISSN 2518-5551

Answer options: 0: Almost always. 1: Often. 2: About half the time. 3: Rarely. 4: Almost never.

4. The level of the government's monitoring over the entry and exit of civil society organizations (CSOs) into public life (CSO entry and exit).

Answer options: 0: Monopolistic control. The government exercises a clear monopoly over the entry and exit of CSOs. Government-funded organizations are allowed to engage in political activities. They are able to support parties or politicians, sponsor forums on public issues, participate in strikes or publicly comment on public officials and politics, organize rallies or demonstrations. The government actively represses violators of the political monopoly.

1: Significant control. The government licenses all CSOs and uses political criteria to ban anti-government CSOs. Some civil society organizations play a limited role in politics independent of the government. The government actively represses CSOs that do not meet political criteria, prohibiting their political activities.

2: Moderate control. Regardless of the partial or total government's ban on independent CSOs, some banned organizations manage to play an active political role. Despite the ban on such organizations, the government does not or cannot repress them because of weakness or political expediency.

3: Minimal control. Regardless of the government's licensing of CSOs, there are constitutional provisions that allow the government to ban organizations or movements that have been engaged in anti-democratic activities in the past (for instance, the ban on neo-fascist or communist organizations in the Federal Republic of Germany). Such a ban is fulfilled under conditions of strict rule of law and independence of the judiciary.

4: Without restrictions. Regardless of whether the government licenses CSOs, the government does not prevent them from forming and operating, except when they are not engaged in activities aimed at violently overthrowing the government.

JOURNAL OF LAW AND POLITICAL SCIENCES (JLPS)

The academic paper analyzes the regulatory and legal fundamentals of interaction of civil society and the government authorities in the system of public administration in Ukraine for the period 2000-2022. Data from the Government Portal (2023) on the legal framework for developing civil society in Ukraine were used for the analysis, namely: laws, Resolutions and Orders of the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine, Orders of the Ministry of Justice, international documents.

IV RESULTS

The National Strategy for Promoting the Development of Civil Society in Ukraine for 2021-2026 noted the increase in the number of civil society institutions during 2016-2020 (Verkhovna Rada of Ukraine, 2023). According to the data of the State Statistics Service of Ukraine, there was an increase in the number of legal entities by organizational and legal forms of business: public organizations – by 22149 (from 70321 as of January 1, 2016 to 92470 as of January 1, 2021), public unions – by 1122 (from 753 to 1875, respectively), religious organizations – by 3390 (from 23261 to 26651, respectively), charitable organizations – by 4428 (from 15384 to 19812, respectively), creative unions (other professional organizations) - by 38 (from 279 to 317, respectively), bodies of self-organization of the population – by 234 (from 1415 to 1649, respectively), trade unions and their associations – by 2392 (from 26321 to 28713, respectively). The above tendencies may affect the interaction level of civil society institutions (CSIs) and public administration bodies. In 2021-2022, there is a sharp increase in registrations of charitable organizations. In April 2022, there is an increase in the issue of supporting the army, the state and vulnerable groups of the population (Vkursi, 2022). Thus, compared to April 2021, there were 12 times more registrations of organizations specializing in charitable activities, in particular, taking into account the possibility of fundraising (Vkursi, 2022).

Compared to other social institutions, the CSIs have a high level of public trust. According to the Institute of Sociology of the National Academy of Sciences of Ukraine, in 2019, 38% of respondents trusted in public organizations and

Vol. (37), issue 2- 2023 P. ISSN 2222-7288 E. ISSN 2518-5551

charitable foundations. In 2021, the level of trust in public organizations increased to 47% (answers of respondents “I rather trust and completely trust” prevailed) (Razumkov Center, 2021). In 2022, the level of trust in humanitarian and charitable organizations was 78% (Razumkov Center, 2022). However, the level of dissemination of civil practices requiring organizational and collective efforts (in particular, participation in the activities of civil society institutions) remained low. The lack of essential legislation is one of the problems hindering the growth of charitable organizations, as indicated by 34% of respondents to the Ukrainian Center for the Study of Public Opinion “Sotsioinform” study in 2019.

A problematic issue is also the low level of civil society institutions’ institutional development, the lack of stable involvement of professional personnel and financial and material resources, sustainable practices of partnership with state authorities, local self-government bodies, and business.

In Ukraine, civil society institutions operate in most spheres of public life, namely: representation of the interests of citizens’ various groups, in the field of protection of human and citizen rights, provision of social and other services, implementation of volunteer and charitable activities, environmental protection, implementation of cultural and educational projects, analysis of the implementation of state policy, monitoring the activities of authorities, conducting anti-corruption activities, etc. Compared to the countries of Eastern and Central Europe, Ukraine has a significantly higher Index of Civil Society Participation (Figure 1).

a) East – Central Europe

b) Ukraine

JOURNAL OF LAW AND POLITICAL SCIENCES (JLPS)

Figure 1. Civil society participation index: CSO consultation, CSO participatory environment, CSO women's participation, 1990 – 2021

Source: V-Dem (2023a).

* Aggregation: The index is formed by taking the point estimates from a Bayesian factor analysis model of the indicators for candidate selection --- national/local (v2psenslnl), CSO consultation (v2cscnsult), CSO participatory environment (v2csptrcpt), and CSO women participation (v2csgender).

For comparison, in the countries of Eastern and Central Europe, the level of consultations is 0,77, the entry and exit of CSOs – 0,98, the participatory environment – 0,64, women's participation level – 1,96. During the period 1991-2021, the participation of CSOs in counseling in Ukraine has grown significantly. However, in general, politicians take into account separate sets of votes. Ukraine also has a low degree of self-organization and voluntary CSOs (0,76 in 1991 and 1,59 in 2021): voluntary public organizations exist, but few people participate in them; there are many different CSOs, but the participation of the population is minimal. In Ukraine, a significant level of government control over the entry and exit of CSOs into public life was revealed (0,68 in 1991 and 1,29 in 2021). That is, the government licenses operating CSOs and uses political criteria to ban CSOs operating against the government. Some civil society organizations play a limited role in politics independent of the government. The government actively represses CSOs that do not meet political criteria, prohibiting their political activity (Figure 2).

Vol. (37), issue 2- 2023 P. ISSN 2222-7288 E. ISSN 2518-5551

Figure 2. Dynamics of the Index of Civil Society Participation in Ukraine and its components in 1990-2021

Source: V-Dem (2023b).

CSIs of Ukraine provide a flexible response to changes in society's needs as a result of the action of external and internal factors. In particular, in recent years, a significant number of public, religious, and charitable organizations have been focused on solving the problems of military personnel, war veterans from among the participants of the anti-terrorist operation of the joint forces, and citizens who suffered as a result of the armed aggression of the Russian Federation. Starting from 2020, CSIs make a significant contribution to preventing the spread of the acute respiratory disease COVID-19 caused by the SARS-CoV-2 coronavirus on the territory of Ukraine, and dealing with its consequences. In Europe as a whole, there is a different level of involving CSOs in the government's activities. The highest level of involving CSOs is observed in the most developed countries of the West, where CSOs are identified as stakeholders in important political areas and have the right to vote (Figure 3).

Figure 3. CSO consultation in Europe, 1991 – 2021

Source: V-Dem (2023c).

The degree of self-organization and voluntary participation of citizens in CSOs is also higher in European countries compared to Ukraine (Figure 4), particularly, in Northern and Western Europe.

Figure 4. CSO participatory environment in Europe, 1991 – 2021

Source: V-Dem (2023c).

European countries also have moderate or minimal control over entry and exit from CSOs (Figure 5). At the same time, some banned CSOs manage to play an active political role in Europe. Minimal control of CSOs’ activities in Europe assumes that there are constitutional provisions allowing the government to ban organizations or movements that have had anti-democratic actions in the past. Such a ban takes place under conditions of the strict rule of law and independence of the judiciary.

Figure 5. CSO entry and exit in Europe, 1991 – 2021

Source: V-Dem (2023c).

The interaction of civil society institutions (CSIs) with the state authorities of Ukraine in accordance with the legislation takes place in the following legal forms:

1. CSIs' participation in the rule-making activity of the state, which is ensured by participation in developing and discussing draft normative legal acts.

2. SCIs' participation in law enforcement activities of the state, which is ensured by:

- full transfer of powers of state bodies;
- transfer of partial powers of state bodies;
- public control.

3. CSIs' participation in law enforcement activities of the state, which is ensured by:

- exercising the right to draw up protocols on administrative offenses;
- CSIs' participation in the activities of internal affairs bodies to ensure the protection of public order;
- exercising the right to take measures together with police officers to stop administrative offenses and crimes;
- CSIs' participation with the bodies of the State Border Service of Ukraine in the protection of the state border.

The activity of the Ukraine-EU Civil Society Platform (CSP) is the example of interaction of CSIs' and state authorities. It was created in May 2014 in accordance with Articles 469-470 of the Association Agreement between Ukraine and the EU. CSP is a body consisting of representatives of Ukraine's civil society on the one hand and members of the European Economic and Social Committee (EESC) on the other. The Platform is one of the four bodies of the Association

JOURNAL OF LAW AND POLITICAL SCIENCES (JLPS)

along with the Council of the Association, the Committee of the Association and the Parliamentary Committee of the Association. The former represent the government and the parliament, while the CSP was created to ensure the proper role of the public in implementing the Association Agreement. The CSP may make recommendations to the Association Council. The Association Committee and the Parliamentary Committee of the Association shall make regular contact with the representatives of the Civil Society Platform in order to obtain their opinion on achieving the Agreement's goals. CSP consists of 15 members – representatives of various sectors of civil society: public associations, trade unions and employers' organizations, which are approved by the Assembly of CSP in accordance with the Regulations: 6 coordinators of working groups; 3 representatives of public associations; 3 representatives of trade unions at the national level; 3 representatives of the employers' organization at the national level.

The introduction of the previously mentioned forms of participating civil society institutions in public administration is determined by a number of normative legal acts. The regulatory and legal basis of interaction includes the constitutional fundamentals of CSIs' activities, the legislative bases of the regulation of various CSIs (political parties, professional unions, charitable organizations, creative unions, religious organizations, youth and children's public organizations, etc.), Decrees of the President of Ukraine, Resolutions and Orders of the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine (CMU), Orders of the Ministry of Justice of Ukraine, international documents. Among the latter, the following ones should be emphasized: the Universal Declaration of Human Rights; International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights; Convention on the Protection of Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms; European Social Charter; Convention "On access to information, public participation in the decision-making process and access to justice on environmental matters (Aarhus Convention)"; Recommendation of the Committee of Ministers of the Council of Europe "On the participation of citizens

Vol. (37), issue 2- 2023 P. ISSN 2222-7288 E. ISSN 2518-5551

in local public life”; Guidelines for public participation in the political decision-making process, Code of best practices for public participation in the decision-making process.

Article 36 of the Constitution of Ukraine states that “citizens of Ukraine have the right to freedom of association in political parties and public organizations for exercising and protecting their rights and freedoms and satisfaction of political, economic, social, cultural and other interests”. Article 38 defines the right of citizens to participate in the management of state affairs.

The regulatory and legal fundamentals of interaction of civil society and government authorities began to develop in the early 2000s, when a number of laws were adopted regarding the various organizations’ activities. The analysis of the changes made to the legislation regulating CSIs’ activities makes it possible to identify the following stages of developing regulatory and legal frameworks: 1) the stage of formation of civil society’s legal fundamentals in 2000-2013 or the stage before the start of the European integration of Ukraine; 2) the stage of integration of the legal framework into EU standards from the beginning of 2014 to 2022 inclusive. At the same time, at the first stage, active changes in the legislation were implemented in 2003-2005, 2007-2009, and 2012-2013. At the second stage, active changes were implemented in 2018-2019, 2021-2022.

Among primary features of the regulatory principles of interacting civil society and government authorities, particular attention is paid the variability of legal conditions, especially, after 2014 and the start of European integration processes. The Law 4572-VI “On Public Associations” dated June 12, 2022 (Verkhovna Rada of Ukraine, 2023) defines the legal and organizational fundamentals of exercising the right to freedom of association guaranteed by the Constitution of Ukraine and international treaties of Ukraine. The effect of Law 4572-VI extends to public relations in the sphere of formation, registration, activity and termination of public associations in Ukraine. The key principles of formation and activity of public associations are defined as follows:

JOURNAL OF LAW AND POLITICAL SCIENCES (JLPS)

- 1) voluntariness;
- 2) self-government;
- 3) free choice of the area of activity;
- 4) equality before the law;
- 5) lack of property interest of their members (participants);
- 6) transparency, openness and publicity.

The legal fundamentals of interaction include as follows: the Law of Ukraine “On Appeals of Citizens”; the Law of Ukraine “On Information”; the Law of Ukraine “On Access to Public Information”; the Law of Ukraine “On the procedure for covering the activities of state authorities and local self-government bodies in Ukraine by mass media”; the Law of Ukraine “On Television and Radio Broadcasting”; the Law of Ukraine “On printed mass media (press) in Ukraine”; the Law of Ukraine “On Social Services”; the Law of Ukraine “On the principles of state regulatory policy in the sphere of economic activity”; the Law of Ukraine “On the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine”; the Law of Ukraine “On the Implementation of Decisions and Application of Practice of the European Court of Human Rights”.

The Decrees of the President of Ukraine determine the strategic principles of developing civil society in Ukraine for a certain period. The role of CSIs is increasing with the processes of European integration. For instance, the Decree of the President of Ukraine dated February 26, 2016 No. 68 “On promoting the development of civil society in Ukraine” and the Decree of the President of Ukraine dated November 4, 2016 No. 487 “Issues of the Coordinating Council for the Promotion of Civil Society Development” were approved. The Decree of the President of Ukraine dated September 27, 2021 No. 487 “On the National Strategy for Promoting the Development of Civil Society in Ukraine for 2021-2026” deserves special attention. The latter defines strategic directions for ensuring the fulfillment of obligations regarding interacting state authorities with

Vol. (37), issue 2- 2023 P. ISSN 2222-7288 E. ISSN 2518-5551

civil society institutions, defined in the Association Agreement between Ukraine and the European Union, the European Atomic Energy Community and their member states.

Resolutions of the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine determine the normative and legal principles of openness, transparency, and participation of civil society in the executive authorities' activities. In fact, the Regulations of the CMU define the procedures for disclosing information, measures for the openness of public authorities, the procedure for facilitating public expertise, the procedure for citizens' interaction and participation in public administration. For instance, the Resolution of the CMU No. 996 "On ensuring public participation in the formation and implementation of state policy" was approved on November 3, 2010. It defines the main requirements for organizing and holding consultations of executive authorities with the public (Verkhovna Rada of Ukraine, 2023). The Resolution of the CMU dated June 13, 2012 No. 671 "Some issues of implementation in Ukraine of the Initiative "Open Government Partnership" determines the basic principles of involving civil society institutions in implementing the Initiative. The provisions of the CMU's Decrees also determine the legal fundamentals for ensuring the openness and interaction of public administration bodies with civil society, the basis of public discussions of social-economic issues, the state communication policy, action plans and measures for interaction.

The legal basis for the activities of religious organizations in Ukraine is the Law on Freedom of Conscience and Religious Associations, enacted on June 6, 1991 (according to the Resolution of the Verkhovna Rada of the Ukrainian SSR of April 23, 1991, N 988-XII). The law was amended in 1992-1996, 2003, 2009, 2012 and 2014, and 2018-2019. The law guarantees the right to freedom of conscience to citizens of Ukraine and ensures its implementation in accordance with the Constitution of Ukraine, the Declaration of State Sovereignty of Ukraine and international law recognized by Ukraine. The law also guarantees social

JOURNAL OF LAW AND POLITICAL SCIENCES (JLPS)

justice, equality, and protection of the rights and legitimate interests of citizens, regardless of their attitude to religion. It defines the duties of the state in relation to religious organizations and the duties of religious organizations to the state and society. The law is aimed at overcoming the negative consequences of state policy on religion and the church. Moreover, it guarantees the creation of favorable conditions for the development of public morality and humanism, civil harmony and cooperation of people regardless of their worldview or religion (Verkhovna Rada of Ukraine, 2023).

According to the Religious Information Service of Ukraine, as of 20.10.2022, 25652 religious organizations were registered with the code of organizational and legal form 825 "Religious organization" (hereinafter RO) (Table 1). The largest number of ROs is in Lviv, Ternopil, Zakarpattia, Volyn, Rivne, and Khmelnytskyi oblasts.

Table 1. Registered ROs in Ukraine as of 20.10.2022

Oblasts of Ukraine and the city of Kyiv*	Number of persons per one registered RO	Registered ROs		Population according to the State Statistics Service of Ukraine as of February 1, 2022	
		N umber	Pe rcentage	N umber of persons	P ercentage
Ternopil oblast	655	1 559	6, 1%	1 020 953	2 ,5%
Volyn oblast	754	1 353	5, 3%	1 020 770	2 ,5%

Vol. (37), issue 2- 2023 P. ISSN 2222-7288 E. ISSN 2518-5551

	Zakarpattia oblast	837	1 486	5, 8%	1 243 721	3 ,0%
	Rivne oblast	852	1 339	5, 2%	1 140 902	2 ,8%
	Khmelnytskyi oblast	896	1 370	5, 3%	1 227 474	3 ,0%
	Chernivtsi oblast	962	9 25	3, 6%	88 9 928	2 ,2%
	Lviv oblast	964	2 568	10 ,0%	2 476 113	6 ,0%
	Ivano-Frankivsk oblast	1 090	1 239	4, 8%	1 350 565	3 ,3%
	Zhytomyr oblast	1 202	9 80	3, 8%	1 177 564	2 ,9%
0	Vinnitsya oblast	1 243	1 213	4, 7%	1 507 738	3 ,7%
1	Kyiv oblast	1 339	1 341	5, 2%	1 795 542	4 ,4%
2	Kherson oblast	1 648	6 07	2, 4%	1 000 370	2 ,4%
3	Chernihiv oblast	1 698	5 64	2, 2%	95 7 665	2 ,3%
4	Poltava oblast	1 775	7 61	3, 0%	1 350 564	3 ,3%

JOURNAL OF LAW AND POLITICAL SCIENCES (JLPS)

5	Cherkasy oblast	1 879	6 17	2, 4%	1 159 200	2 ,8%
6	Sumy oblast	2 036	5 08	2, 0%	1 034 364	2 ,5%
7	Kirovohrad oblast	2 051	4 40	1, 7%	90 2 275	2 ,2%
8	Mykolaiiv oblast	2 272	4 80	1, 9%	1 090 492	2 ,7%
9	Odesa oblast	2 430	9 67	3, 8%	2 349 749	5 ,7%
0	Zaporizhzhia oblast	2 525	6 48	2, 5%	1 636 322	4 ,0%
1	Dnipropetrovs'k oblast	2 624	1 179	4, 6%	3 093 151	7 ,5%
2	Donetsk oblast	2 946	1 377	5, 4%	4 056 405	9 ,9%
3	City of Kyiv	3 207	9 20	3, 6%	2 950 702	7 ,2%
4	Luhansk oblast	3 668	5 73	2, 2%	2 101 653	5 ,1%
5	Kharkiv oblast	4 069	6 38	2, 5%	2 596 250	6 ,3%
	Ukraine *	1 603	2 5 652	10 0,0%	41 130 432	1 00,0%

Vol. (37), issue 2- 2023 P. ISSN 2222-7288 E. ISSN 2518-5551

* Excluding the temporarily occupied Autonomous Republic of Crimea and the city of Sevastopol. The State Statistics Service of Ukraine does not have relevant data on the population there.

Source: Religious Information Service of Ukraine (2023).

In 2019, Ukraine approved the Regulation on the Council for Cooperation with Churches and Religious Associations under the Ministry of Education and Science of Ukraine. The purpose of the Council is to create effective organizational and legal conditions for citizens to exercise their constitutional right to participate in the management of public affairs (Ministry of Education and Science of Ukraine, 2023a). The body should ensure the openness of the Ministry of Education and Science of Ukraine, take into account public opinion in the process of preparing and organizing the implementation of its decisions, promote comprehensive freedom of conscience and further harmonization of church-state relations in the field of education. Its responsibilities also include maintaining a constant dialogue with churches and religious organizations to more effectively use their potential in the educational process (Ministry of Education and Science of Ukraine, 2023a).

It is crucial to note the active work of a significant number of members of the Public Council in the context of the Russian Federation's aggression against Ukraine to provide the necessary assistance to IDPs (including educators), resettle them in the western regions of Ukraine and abroad, provide the necessary humanitarian aid, etc. (Ministry of Education and Science of Ukraine, 2023b).

V. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

The primary issues of the regulatory and legal fundamentals of interacting civil society and the government authorities are limited outdated political approaches to its development in Ukraine and the CEE countries as a whole. Similar conclusions are drawn in the scientific works of Phillips & Smith (2011), Anheier, Lang &

JOURNAL OF LAW AND POLITICAL SCIENCES (JLPS)

Toepler (2019), where the authors note analogous barriers to CSI development. In practice, a clear normative approach to stimulating the activities of CS, managing the regulatory framework and regulatory environment has not been developed in the CEE countries and Ukraine, in particular. Changing political conditions and the reduction of the democracy level also negatively affect the legal framework development (Anders & Lorenz, 2021).

On the contrary, regulation is characterized by a fiscal nature. It is built on the idea of public utility, voluntariness, benevolence, transparency. At the same time, the level of trust in social institutions of Ukraine in society increased from 38% in 2019 to 47% in 2021. In society, CSI is perceived more as a charitable activity, and not as an organization defending the political, economic, social and other interests of Ukrainian society. CSIs are also perceived as monitoring organizations exercising public control over government activities although public control is only one form of interaction. At the same time, government authorities actually control CSIs' activities. The example of Ukraine and the CEE countries shows that the government exercises moderate or minimal control over the work of CSIs. The existing legal and regulatory framework determines the legal and organizational basis for the activity of CS in Ukraine. In other words, it provides for a "light" form of the regulatory framework and little state support. The considered example of the work of the Ukraine-EU Civil Society Platform (CSP), which was created at the request of Ukraine's accession to the EU, indicates its minimal activity in 2016-2018 and lack of activity in 2020-2022. Thus, Ukrainian society actually has an average level of trust in the CSI. As a result, it does not contribute to the active development of the CSI as a whole, the full participation of citizens in public administration.

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Vol. (37), issue 2- 2023 P. ISSN 2222-7288 E. ISSN 2518-5551

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Contents of Vol. No. (37) of issue (2) April-2023

- 1- **Specificity Of Procedural Rules In The Face Of Terrorist Crime Descriptive And Analytical Study. Dr. Faris Bin Saleh Al-Faris- Saudi Arabia. P. 10.**
- 2- **Current Mechanism Of Implementation Of Administrative And Legal Ensuring Of The Right To Freedom Of Intellectual Activity As A Necessary Condition For Managing The Public Officials' Integrity. Petro Makushev and Others. Ukraine. p. 33.**
- 3- **Protection Of Intellectual Property Rights In Jordan's Constitution According To The Latest Amendments (A Comparative Study). Dr. Shatha Ahmad Al-Assaf. And Others. Jordan, p. 55.**
- 4- **Trade Usage In Terms Of Proof And Appeal Under Saudi Law. Dr. Mohammed Sulaiman Alnasyanp. , Saudi Arabia. p. 81.**
- 5- **Legal Status And Principles Of Cryptocurrency Circulation. Lyudmila Fokina. And Others. Russia , p. 101.**
- 6- **The Legal Basis For The Property Owner's Liability For Damages Resulting From A Breach Of Neighborhood Restrictions In Jordanian Legislation(Overhangs And Skylights Are A Model) Dr. Najm Riad Al-Rabadi And Others. P. 120.**
- 7- **Non - Physical Punishments Contained In The Holy Qur'an. Dr. Abdullah Saleh Abdullah Alomar. Saudi Arabia. P. 143.**
- 8- **The Concept Of Humanitarian Intervention In The Context Of Constitutional And Legal Policy Of The State. Viktoriia Ternavska And Others. Ukraine. P. 161.**
- 9- **Impact Of Compensation On The Civil Liability Resulting From The Disclosure Of The Bank Secret. "Mohammad Ashraf" Khalid Ali Al-Qheiw And Others. Jordan. p. 173.**
- 10- **The Impact Of A Learning Management System Of Viet Nam Education Law On Student Performance Through Academic Motivation. Duong Cam Tu And Others. Viet Nam, p. 192.**
- 11- **A Legal Study On Proportionality Of The Punishment To The Crime. Hoda Ahmad Albarrak. Saudi Arabia. p. 229.**
- 12- **Violation Of The Sanctity Of Real Estate According To The Provisions Of Jordanian Legislation. Dr. Ali Mohammed Al Zoubi, , Jordan. P. 246.**
- 13- **Electronic Testimony And Its Probative Value, A Study In The Jordanian Legislation, Dr .Mashal Mufleh Jarrah. And Others. Jordan. 271.**
- 14- **Protection of New Plant Varieties In The Saudi System In Light Of The Upov Agreement. Dr Ahmed Mohamed Fathy Elkholy, Saudi Arabia. p. 298.**
- 15- **Policy For Improving The Quality Of Manufacturing Human Resources Of Vietnam Tea Corporation: Research From Current Vietnam Law. Phuong Huu Tung. And Others. Viet Nam. p.324.**
- 16- **Legal And Regulatory Fundamentals Of Interaction Of Civil Society And Government Authorities In The System Of Public Administration. Halyna Shaulska. And Others. Ukraine. p. 344.**
- 17- **Revenues And Expenditures of Local Budgets In Conditions Of Decentralization Of Power: Legal Aspect. Nataliia Vorotina And Others. Ukraine. P. 368**